

Predicting T cell receptor specificity with graph attention networks

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Abstract. T cells play a pivotal role in adaptive immunity by recognizing a vast array of antigens through their T cell receptors (TCRs). Advances in high-throughput sequencing have enabled unprecedented profiling of TCR repertoires, enabling the computational prediction of TCR-antigen associations. Existing machine learning approaches, including deep learning and clustering algorithms, have shown promise in identifying patterns within TCR sequences, particularly through features such as complementarity-determining region 3 (CDR3) sequences and V(D)J gene usage. However, many existing models are constrained by their architectural limitations, and often relying on feature concatenation to achieve multi-modal analysis. In this study, we proposed an algorithm that integrates deep learning techniques with immune repertoire data to enhance TCR specificity prediction. By leveraging language models and graph attention networks, our framework systematically identifies patterns that correlate with antigen recognition, improving predictive accuracy and enhancing multi-modal analysis of TCR sequencing data. Experiment results obtained from two public datasets showed that our method can accurately predict TCR-epitope associations. Our study also underscores the importance of integrating biomolecular networks and advanced language models to uncover fundamental principles of immune responses and translate them into clinically relevant applications.

Keywords: Graph attention networks, T cell receptor specificity, Heterogeneous network, BERT

1 Introduction

The ability of T cells to recognize and respond to a diverse array of antigens is a cornerstone of adaptive immunity. This recognition is mediated by T cell receptors (TCRs), which bind to peptide-major histocompatibility complex (pMHC) molecules on antigen-presenting cells. The sheer diversity of TCRs, estimated to be in the millions within an individual, poses significant challenges for understanding how these receptors discern specific antigens. Advances in high-throughput sequencing technologies have enabled researchers to profile TCR repertoires at an unprecedented scale, revealing the complexity and variability

of TCR usage in different contexts, including infections, cancer, and autoimmune diseases.

Despite the wealth of data generated through next-generation sequencing (NGS), the study of TCR repertoires is often hampered by high-dimensionality issues and the noise inherent in biological data. Machine learning approaches have gained traction as a means to address these challenges, providing computational tools that can leverage large datasets to infer TCR specificity and enhance our understanding of immune responses. Recent studies have highlighted the potential of machine learning models, such as deep learning and unsupervised clustering techniques, to classify TCRs based on their sequences and associated antigen specificity [5, 6, 11, 12, 15, 16]. These models utilize various features, including complementarity-determining region 3 (CDR3) sequences and V/D/J gene usage, to generate insights into TCR behavior. For example, NetTCR employs a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture which took the amino acid sequences of both the TCR and the epitope to predict their associations [5]. However, constrained by their architectural, existing algorithms rely on feature concatenation to integrate multiple data modalities. Meanwhile, many algorithms encode CDR3 sequences using BLOSUM matrices, which may fail to fully capture structural and functional patterns within TCR sequences, thereby limiting their ability to accurately model antigen recognition [4, 11, 16, 17].

To address these limitations, we propose an algorithm that leverages graph neural network (GNN) with pre-trained language models to derive meaningful insights into TCR specificity prediction. By leveraging sequence features extracted by language models and sequence similarities of TCRs and epitopes, our framework aims to systematically identify patterns that correlate with antigen recognition. This approach not only seeks to improve the predictive accuracy of TCR specificity inference but also aims to facilitate the development of TCR-based biomarkers with potential clinical applications.

By combining computational techniques with biological insights, we aim to bridge the gap between TCR repertoire analysis and practical applications in immunotherapy and vaccine development. Our findings emphasize the need for multi-modal analysis in the field, encouraging the integration of biomolecular networks and language models to unlock the full potential of TCR research in understanding immune responses and informing clinical practices.

2 Methods

The workflow of our proposed algorithm is shown in Fig. 1. First, the available α and/or β -chain CDR3 variable sequences, and epitope sequences are provided to ProteinBERT, a pre-trained deep learning model specifically designed for protein sequences, to extract raw representations [2]. Unlike many language models, ProteinBERT is optimized for the unique characteristics of proteins, incorporating both local and global representations. The model consists of six transformer-like blocks that process local and global representations and was pre-trained over $\sim 10^6$ proteins from UniProtKB/UniRef90 [1, 18], making it an ideal tool for

Fig. 1. Workflow of our proposed algorithm

encoding amino acid sequences. The latent representations learned by ProteinBERT were used as raw features to represent the TCR and epitope sequences in our study. In the meantime, V/D/J gene usage is also labeled coded and concatenated at the end of the sequence representations.

Second, a heterogeneous graph was created using pair-wise similarities among TCR sequences and epitope sequences. This graph comprises two distinct types of nodes: TCR node and epitope node, each initialized with respective raw feature sets. For capturing intra-node relationships, each TCR/epitope are connected with their top N most similar nodes by weighted edges, reflecting the degree of similarity. $N = 15$ and $N = 10$ were selected to construct the TCR similarity network and the epitope similarity network, respectively, ensuring the formation of a fully connected graph. Furthermore, cross-node interactions are encoded as edges between TCR and epitope nodes. These edges represent known biological associations obtained from public database. Due to the limitation of metadata provided in our dataset, we used the k-mer algorithm and cosine similarity to compute the TCR similarities and epitope similarities [14]. In the future, as more datasets with detailed metadata become available, we could leverage algorithms like TCRdist [11] to compute similarities more effectively.

Finally, a graph attention network (GAT) architecture was used to predict TCR specificity. GAT leverages the network’s connectivity and iteratively updates node representations by aggregating information from their neighbors through a message-passing mechanism [19, 20]. Our model comprises dual processing pipelines designed specifically for TCR and epitope nodes, respectively. For both node types, the input features are initially transformed through the first GAT layer into a higher-dimensional hidden space, followed by two additional GAT layers designed to further refine feature representations. Each graph attention layer employs multi-head attention mechanisms to adaptively aggregate information from neighboring nodes, thereby improving feature expressiveness and robustness. Specifically, four attention heads were used in each layer to enhance representation learning. A ReLU activation function is applied after each graph convolution operation to introduce non-linearity. Additionally, dropout layers with a probability of 0.3 are used to prevent over-fitting and improve generalization. The model differentiates itself by its edge classifier that employs a fully connected layer to predict edge associations, effectively synthesizing node-specific information from both TCR and epitope domains. This architecture supports the extraction of interaction dynamics between TCR and epitope nodes, making it highly effective for tasks characterized by intricate biological networks.

2.1 Datasets

In this study, we evaluated the performance of our algorithm using two datasets. The first dataset was downloaded from the VDJdb database (<https://vdjdb.cdr3.net/>), which contains experimentally validated TCR sequences and their antigen-specific interactions across multiple organisms, tissues, and biological contexts [7]. We specifically selected human and mouse TCR-epitope associations for analysis. To

refine the dataset, we filtered TCR clonotypes based on confidence scores, retaining only annotations with a score of 1 as true positive samples. Negative samples were randomly selected from entries with a confidence score of 0, indicating no known association between the TCR and its corresponding epitope. In total, the human dataset contains 3,847 positive associations, and the mouse dataset contains 1,718 positive samples. To ensure a balanced dataset, the number of negative samples was set equal to the number of positive samples.

The second dataset was obtained from [3], which consists of 332 TCR-epitope binding pairs from two unique SARS-CoV-2 epitopes. The first epitope is recognized by 304 cognate TCRs, while the second epitope is recognized by 28 cognate TCRs. The dataset also includes the same number of negative TCR-epitope pairs.

2.2 Evaluation

To validate the model, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the area under the curve (AUC) were used to evaluate the performance of the model in predicting TCR-epitope association. ROC curve characterizes true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) under different thresholds, providing a comprehensive measure of the model’s overall performance.

10-fold cross-validation (CV) was used to generate prediction scores and assess the model’s effectiveness. The dataset was randomly split into 10 subsets, with each fold serving as a test set once while the remaining nine were used for training. This process was repeated across all folds, and the final evaluation metrics were computed by averaging the results. To mitigate potential bias introduced by random splitting, 10-fold CV was performed 3 times, and the average results were used for final metric calculation.

The proposed model was compared with a baseline model and NetTCR [5]. For baseline, we selected the GradientBoost classifier because it is a widely used, robust machine learning method known for its ability to handle structured tabular data and prevent overfitting through boosting. The input to the GradientBoost model was the raw feature matrix extracted by ProteinBERT. We selected NetTCR because it is a deep learning-based method specifically designed for predicting TCR-epitope associations. NetTCR takes the amino acid sequences of both the TCR and the epitope as input and uses a CNN architecture to perform the predictions.

3 Results

Fig. 2 presents the ROC curves for the VDJdb human dataset, comparing our model with NetTCR and GradientBoost. Our model achieved an AUC of 0.990, demonstrating near-perfect discrimination between positive and negative samples. GradientBoost performed moderately well with an AUC of 0.841, while NetTCR showed limited predictive ability (AUC = 0.552). These results highlight the strong advantage of our approach over existing methods.

Fig. 2. ROC curve obtained from VDJdb human dataset.

Fig. 3. ROC curve obtained from VDJdb mouse dataset.

Fig. 4. ROC curve obtained from the COVID-19 dataset.

Similar trends were observed in Fig. 3, which shows the results for the VDJdb mouse dataset. Our model again outperformed the baselines, achieving an AUC of 0.979, whereas GradientBoost and NetTCR reached AUCs of 0.624 and 0.522, respectively. This consistency across datasets underscores the robustness and generalizability of our approach.

Fig. 4 further supports these findings, presenting results from the SARS-CoV-2 dataset. Our model maintained superior performance with an AUC of 0.982, compared to GradientBoost (AUC = 0.461) and NetTCR (AUC = 0.611). Notably, GradientBoost showed lower than random performance, likely due to the high dimensionality and limited sample size of the input data, which challenges traditional machine learning models.

4 Discussion

Predicting TCR antigen specificity is a key objective in systems immunology, with significant implications for vaccine development, immunotherapy, and autoimmune disease research. The advent of NGS has dramatically increased the availability of TCR sequencing data, enabling computational approaches to predict TCR specificity. However, accurately reconstructing TCR-antigen interactions remains a major challenge.

Many existing models are constrained by their architectural limitations, often relying on feature concatenation to integrate multiple data modalities. Meanwhile, many algorithms encode CDR3 sequences using BLOSUM matrices, which may fail to fully capture structural and functional patterns within TCR sequences, thereby limiting their ability to accurately model antigen recognition [4, 11, 16, 17].

Furthermore, the generalizability of predictive models is hindered by the limited scope of available datasets, which capture only a fraction of all possible TCR-ligand interactions. While previous studies have shown that incorporating both α -chain and β -chain sequences enhances predictive performance [9], many large-scale TCR-ligand databases, such as VDJdb, only provide β -chain CDR3 sequences. This further restricts the applicability of computational approaches, as α -chain information is crucial for antigen recognition and binding specificity.

Recent advancements in single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) and single-cell TCR sequencing (scTCR-seq) have enabled a deeper exploration of the transcriptional profiles of neoantigen-specific and tumor-reactive T cells within the tumor microenvironment. These technologies offer an opportunity to develop predictors of private T cell receptor-based therapies, capable of identifying tumor-reactive T cells for personalized immunotherapy. Researchers have used these technologies to identify tumor-reactive TCRs [8,10,13,21], and Pétremand et al. have applied 21 baseline models on scRNA-seq data to predict tumor reactive T cells [15]. Despite their success, most of these studies focus on expression profiles and gene signatures, and CDR3 sequence information are not used in their models, which limit their generalizability in predicting TCR specificity in non-tumor studies. We believe a model that can integrate both CDR3 sequences and gene expression profiles could fully exploit the complete spectrum of biologically relevant features and improve predictive accuracy and clinical applicability. A graph neural network is capable of such multi-modal integration of both sequence and gene expression patterns within scRNA-seq and scTCRseq data.

In this study, we constructed a heterogeneous network using two public datasets and applied a GAT model to predict TCR specificity. ProteinBert was used to encode the CDR3 sequences. Although gene expression data were not integrated in the model due to data availability, results showed that a language model can effectively capture sequence-level features from TCR and antigen amino acid sequences, while GAT can better leverage structural relationships and sequence distance metrics to improve predictive accuracy. We are currently collecting single cell datasets from [10,15] and will further validate the model's performance on predicting tumor-reactive TCRs when datasets are available. The strategies used for similarity matrix could also be improved once more meta-data is available from these new datasets. As language models and graph-based learning approaches become increasingly ubiquitous in computational biology, algorithms such as the one presented in this work will play a critical role in identifying and characterizing relevant biological signals. This, in turn, will enhance our understanding of TCR-antigen interactions and uncover complex genomic patterns embedded within large-scale immunological datasets.

5 Conclusion

The development of a robust and generalizable algorithm for predicting TCR specificity is critical for immunology research. In this study, we proposed an algorithm leverage ProteinBert and GATs to integrate meaningful features of

TCR sequences and TCR similarities and successfully improve the prediction accuracy. Experiments on two datasets demonstrate that our model is capable of predicting TCR specificity. The source code for the algorithm is available at <https://github.com/GenTensor/graphTCR>. One limitation of our study is that the datasets we used for evaluation did not contain paired gene expression data. We are currently collecting scRNA-seq and scTCRseq datasets from latest studies and will further improve the algorithm with more modalities and new sequence similarity strategies in the future.

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